

Opportunities for Ophthalmology Research in Large Research Cohorts Workshop

*A National Eye Institute, National Institute of Biomedical
Imaging and Bioengineering, and All of Us Research Program
Workshop*

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Hybrid Meeting

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Acronym Definitions

ACHM	achromatopsia
AMD	age-related macular degeneration
All of Us	<i>All of Us</i> Research Program
AD/ADRD	Alzheimer's disease and Alzheimer's disease related dementias
AI	artificial intelligence
AI-READI	The Artificial Intelligence Ready and Equitable Atlas for Diabetes Insights
Bridge2AI	Bridge to Artificial Intelligence Program
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
EHR	electronic health record
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GWAS	genome-wide association study
IOP	interocular pressure
IRIS	Intelligent Research in Sight
MacTel	macular telangiectasia
MCI	mild cognitive impairment
MRI	magnetic resonance imaging
NEI	National Eye Institute
NIBIB	National Institute for Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering
NIH	National Institutes of Health
OCP	Ocular Cicatricial Pemphigoid
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
OCTA	Optical Coherence Tomography Angiography
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
ONC	Office of National Coordinator for Health Information Technology
ORA	Ocular Response Analyzers
QUARTZ	QUantitative Analysis of Retinal Vessel Topology
SLO	scanning laser ophthalmoscopy
SDOH	social determinants of health
UKB	UK Biobank
VAMPIRE	Vessel Assessment and Measurement Platform for Images of the Retina
WGS	whole genome sequencing

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Executive Summary

Introduction

Background

Ocular imaging is crucial for the diagnosis and management of the most common eye diseases. Data analysis and image processing methods have further enhanced the utility of ocular imaging for secondary digital health research. Combining the objective analysis of retinal images with demographic and biomedical data enables a variety of research applications, including association studies correlating imaging biomarkers to systemic disease, investigations into the social and biomedical associations of eye health disparities, and the development of tools for improving eye disease prevention and treatment. To date, this research is largely limited by the lack of publicly available disease-agnostic cohorts, inconsistently applied meta-data standards, data quality, and gaps in additional clinical data.

Opportunities

The potential inclusion of ocular imaging data into the *All of Us* Research Program (*All of Us*) dataset provides a unique opportunity to address many of these issues and empower new opportunities for research. To discuss the opportunities and challenges surrounding incorporating ocular imaging data, NIH partners at NEI, NIBIB, and the *All of Us* Research Program organized a workshop with experts in vision science, ophthalmology, imaging technology, data science, and health disparities research. This workshop explored the current state of imaging informatics in the vision research field, opportunities to expand research with large retinal imaging cohorts, and the data and analytical tools needed to advance this research. This document will summarize the presentations, panel discussions, and key findings from the workshop.

Retinal Imaging Databases and Current Research

UK Biobank Eye and Vision Datasets

The UK Biobank (UKB) is a prospective cohort study with over 500,000 participants that provides a baseline examination of lifestyle, environment, personal and family history, physical measures, genotypic data, and a repository of biological samples. Participants are followed for a 20-year period to gather information on disease outcomes. In 2008, UKB added an eye and vision study. This study consists of a 10-minute examination to collect data on participants' visual acuity, auto-refraction, interocular pressure (IOP) and corneal biomechanics, fundus photography, and optical coherence tomography (OCT). UKB has baseline eye and vision data for 129,761 people and retinal photographs and OCT images for 87,642 people. UKB provides data to researchers on participant biomarkers, health outcomes, answers from online questionnaires, genetics, whole body magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and COVID-19 infection statistics. At the end of 2022, UKB launched a new eye and vision reimaging study, which allows for eye scanning during the UKB MRI sequence to generate ocular biomarkers for mild cognitive impairment and dementia.

All of Us Research Program

The *All of Us* Research Program (*All of Us*) aims to produce a large-cohort dataset of at least 1 million participants who reflect the diversity of the U.S. population with purposeful inclusion of communities previously underrepresented in biomedical research. At the time of the workshop, *All of Us* had 625,000 participants and access to 361,000 electronic health records (EHRs). In 2020, *All of Us* launched the [Researcher Workbench](#), a cloud-based platform where researchers can securely access a broad range of participant-shared data. This platform offers participant survey responses, physical measures, genomic arrays, and whole genome sequencing data, as well as EHR and Fitbit data. *All of Us* data harmonizes data using the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model. Relevant and high potential research opportunities for *All of Us* include studies predicting eye and systemic diseases using OCT, linking retinal diseases with genetic data, assessing health disparities in ocular diseases, and promoting drug target discovery.

Novel Insights from Aging Research

In partnership with Kaiser Permanente, researchers at the University of Washington conducted a longitudinal study of individuals over age 65. Enrollees were required to be cognitively normal at the beginning of the study and were assessed via cognitive tests every 2 years. Researchers analyzed eye image data collected as part of this study to determine whether participants with age-related macular degeneration, glaucoma, or diabetic retinopathy were at risk for developing Alzheimer's disease and Alzheimer's disease related dementias (AD/ADRD). Each of these types of eye disease was associated with significantly high risk for AD/ADRD. A follow-up study showed that diabetic retinopathy alone is a significant risk factor for developing AD/ADRD. Research demonstrating novel connections between eye diseases and neuropathy may help clinicians identify interventions that can help lower these risks. A recent study, which received significant media attention, demonstrated a 30 percent decrease in risk for AD/ADRD for individuals who received cataract surgery compared to those with untreated cataracts.

Optical Coherence Tomography and Large Cohort Studies

OCT imaging has changed clinical practice and opened new areas of understanding for both clinicians and biomedical researchers. It can measure the thickness of retinal layers, detect lesions, and evaluate changes to the fiber of the optic nerve. OCT is one of the primary methods for evaluating the retina mostly because it is noninvasive to patients, reproducible, and relatively easy for clinicians to interpret. Recent advancement in OCT-based imaging has shown promising improvements in measurement sensitivity and intraoperative clinical use. In addition to use in vision care, OCT imaging shows promise detecting biomarkers of neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer disease and dementia. OCT Angiography (OCTA) is an extension of OCT that enables 3D imaging of the retinal vasculature, with applications to diagnosing and studying both eye-related and systemic diseases. OCTA provides sufficient detail to detect morphometric characteristics of the retinal vascular system associated with future risk of cardiovascular diseases.

OCT is useful in detecting ocular diseases, guiding therapies, evaluating outcomes, and finding novel associations between anatomy and genetics. A 2017 study showed that OCT can be used to characterize the natural progression of achromatopsia in order to identify the therapeutic window for this intervention. Another study, in macular telangiectasia patients, showed that OCT changes provided the major outcome variable for the conduct of a successful randomized clinical trial. In addition, researchers using OCT images in the UK Biobank dataset were able to produce novel connections between genetics and retinal anatomy.

Ophthalmic Research Using the *All of Us* Cohort Dataset

Researchers at the University of California, San Diego built a single-center model to predict the need for glaucoma surgery and validated their model using *All of Us* dataset. One aim from this study was to share insights from use of the *All of Us* Researcher Workbench with ophthalmologists and vision scientists. Predictors for glaucoma progression included certain vital signs, physical measurements, comorbid conditions, and medications. Furthermore, a predictive model trained using the *All of Us* Researcher Workbench—which has a diverse participant cohort—achieved superior predictive performance compared to single-center models, highlighting the utility of diverse cohorts for developing new predictive models.

Opportunities for Advancing Research

Systemic Diseases Research Opportunities

Several high-impact research areas could be explored and enabled by adding ocular imaging to the *All of Us* dataset. Research into neurodegenerative diseases, such as AD/ADRD, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis, are hard to diagnosis and treat. Large-scale studies using new technologies on retinal imaging have the potential to revolutionize disease detection, track progression, and explore therapeutic opportunities. Vascular disease is another particularly fruitful area of research that could harness eye imaging data within *All of Us* because vascular disease has been linked to a number of other diseases, including diabetes. Current OCT imaging studies of ocular cicatricial pemphigoid (OCP) have detected subtle retinal changes correlated to cardiovascular and metabolic diseases; and detection of eye trauma via OCT has applications for research for national defense. The relatively inexpensive and noninvasive use of eye scanning may also advance biomarker discovery and early detection of risk factors for immune and inflammatory disease, especially in vulnerable populations.

Challenges in Diverse Representation in Ophthalmological Research

Ocular imaging coupled with *All of Us* longitudinal data can enable researchers to develop new risk models for disease. Relevant data collected by *All of Us* may include genetics and social determinants of health data over an extended course of time. However, large-scale data collection also raises questions of bias and the potential to exacerbate bias. EHR data can be biased because they are input by a clinician, whereas an ocular image produced by a machine may have more objective value and could reduce bias. If the use of *All of Us* ocular imaging datasets leads to a finding that is perceived to be undesirable related to an underrepresented

group, then new stigmas and biases both inside and outside this group could arise. These are broad challenges that impact not only *All of Us*, but the field as a whole.

Challenges in Building Platforms and Tools for Ocular Imaging in *All of Us*

Selecting the Most Useful Image Types

Panel members considered the most useful ocular imaging data for *All of Us* to capture. They agreed that OCT imaging is essential, but *All of Us* stakeholders must select the specific device to be used to collect these imaging data since it is challenging to compare the same image modality captured on devices offered by different manufacturers. The panel also recommended that color fundus photography and optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) be collected by *All of Us* and made available to researchers. Some devices can combine these modalities, which may help reduce costs and reduce the amount of time required to acquire the images. Collection of volumetric data, retinal thickness, and segmentation layer thickness represented in structured data tables could also be useful.

Data storage requirements and associated costs present challenges to collecting imaging data. En-face OCT images generate smaller file sizes than other data types and should be made available for researchers, at a minimum. Data gleaned from OCT, such as layer thicknesses, are often used by researchers rather than analyzing the image itself, which provides a compelling reason to extract segmentation OCT data. Although full 3D OCT image volumes can be large, it was recommended that they should also be available somewhere as they provide useful information for comprehensive analysis.

Creation and Curation of Metadata

Several factors affect the types of metadata that could enable research applications, including interoperability, standardization, and ease of use. *All of Us* could serve as a use case for applying Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) interoperability standards, which may encourage vendors to adopt these standards.

Physiological measures, such as visual acuity, axial length, IOP, auto-refraction, visual field, and corneal biomechanics, were all identified by meeting participants as potentially useful metadata; however, no consensus was reached regarding which measures were most valuable. The cost to collect these measures is a concern, and it is worth noting that UKB conducted a value analysis on costs per participant to develop its protocol. Information from EHRs about prior cataract surgery and other eye surgeries would be helpful for researchers to have access to, as well.

Meeting panelists were divided on the best approach to creating phenotypic or clinical metadata to curate along with ocular image collections. Some panelists expressed reservations about automated phenotyping without human input; however, most panelists recognized that bias remains an issue for any potential metadata, especially metadata captured through

ingestion from EHRs. Computational phenotyping for glaucoma was considered worth pursuing, because of the frequency of misdiagnoses.

Meeting Summary

Welcome and Program Introduction

Kerry Goetz, MS, National Eye Institute

Michael F. Chiang, MD, National Eye Institute

Bruce Tromberg, PhD, National Institute for Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering

Ms. Goetz welcomed meeting participants to the Opportunities for Ophthalmology Research in Large Research Cohorts Workshop. The purpose of this workshop is to identify scientific opportunities that can be addressed through the inclusion of retinal images and eye health data in the *All of Us* Research Program, as well as specific data needs, analytical tools, and other resources necessary to support these scientific opportunities. The National Eye Institute (NEI) values the benefits of big data science for knowledge discovery, which can improve approaches to disease prevention and treatment—and is a central theme of this workshop. Ms. Goetz noted that Dr. Chiang and Dr. Denny began the discussions that would lead to this workshop in 2020.

Dr. Chiang asked workshop participants to consider the metaphor “the eye is the window to the soul” in the context of how ocular images can help to predict numerous systemic diseases. Ophthalmology is a leading domain for artificial intelligence (AI) because of the large volume of ocular imaging data coupled with clinical outcomes data. A 2018 [study](#) showed that autonomous AI can identify the presence of diabetic retinopathy from a retinal image taken in a primary care setting, demonstrating the research opportunities in analyzing large datasets of ocular images. Adding ocular imaging data to *All of Us* would increase researcher access to ocular health data. NEI has also collaborated with the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology (ONC) to promote the adoption of imaging standards and interoperability by device manufacturers. This effort will lead to improved data availability in partnership with *All of Us*.

Dr. Tromberg highlighted the significant opportunities for partnership between the technical community at the National Institute for Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering (NIBIB) and *All of Us* to enable widespread application of the most advanced instrumentation and technologies to improve care. During the pandemic, NIBIB improved methods of validating technologies in order to scale them for broad community use, which revealed an important role for NIBIB in guiding the application of these technologies to collect data for *All of Us*. In particular, NIBIB prioritizes optical coherence tomography (OCT) for ocular imaging because of its versatility and the ability to non-invasively image the back of the eye as well as data rich nature of OCT images to enable biomarker discovery and disease diagnosis and prediction. In partnership with *All of Us* and NEI, NIBIB can provide expertise on the provenance and the computational approaches necessary to extract research insights from collected data.

Current Landscape of Retinal Imaging Research and Databases

UK Biobank: Scope of Eye and Vision Data

Paul J. Foster, PhD FRCS(ed), FRCOphth FRCS(Eng), University College of London

The UK Biobank (UKB) is a prospective cohort study with over 500,000 participants that provides a baseline examination of lifestyle, environment, personal and family history, physical measures, and genotypic data derived from biological samples, as well as 20-year follow-up assessment of potential disease outcomes. Moorfields Eye Hospital and University College of London convened a team of researchers to build an eye and vision study to incorporate into the UKB. This team published a [report](#) on the design and methods of the UKB Eye and Vision Consortium. The consortium's study involved a 10-minute examination to collect participant data on visual acuity, auto-refraction, interocular pressure (IOP), and corneal biomechanics, and fundus photo and macular OCT. Instrumentation used for this study included Tomey RC-5000 for autorefractometry, Reichert Ocular Response Analyzers (ORA) for IOP and corneal biomechanics, and Topcon 3D OCT 1000 Mk2 for fundus photo and macular OCT.

Organizing the large volume of eye and vision data was a significant challenge. Researchers at Topcon laboratories in New Jersey, in collaboration with the team conducting the UKB eye study, applied a data segmentation algorithm to make the data usable for researchers. The UKB study also incorporates retinal viscometry from other collaborations, principally the QUantitative Analysis of Retinal Vessel Topology (QUARTZ) group and the Vessel Assessment and Measurement Platform for Images of the REtina (VAMPIRE) group.

Overall, UKB has baseline eye data for 129,761 people and retinal photographs and OCT for 87,642 people. UKB provides data on biomarkers, health outcomes, survey responses, genetics, whole body magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) imaging, and COVID-19 infections. The most widely accessed data are genotyping and whole genome sequencing (WGS) data. Ocular imaging data from the UKB has enabled researchers to conduct [studies](#) predicting the incidence of diseases. A new eye and vision reimaging study was launched at the end of 2022, which enables scanning during the UKB MRI sequence to generate ocular biomarkers for mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and dementia. This study utilizes the Topcon Triton 3D widescan OCT, retinal photography, and will also assess autorefractometry, keratometry, as well as cortical vision function using a broken letters reading test. The UKB tracks publications from researchers using its datasets, which include numerous academic centers and private organizations, such as Google. Through a recent [study](#) using the UKB cohort, researchers developed an algorithm that can detect Parkinson's disease up to seven years prior to standard diagnosis by using retinal images and AI. This is a great example of how the retina provides a minimally invasive window into the central nervous system and can be imaged rapidly using modern high-resolution devices.

Scientific Opportunities with the *All of Us* Research Program

Josh Denny, MD, MS, All of Us Research Program

The *All of Us* mission is to accelerate health research and medical breakthroughs enabling individualized prevention, treatment, and care for all of us. *All of Us* seeks to nurture partnerships with at least 1 million participants who reflect the diversity of the U.S. population; deliver to researchers one of the largest biomedical datasets that is broadly available and secure; and catalyze an ecosystem of communities, researchers, and funders to make *All of Us* a sustainable platform for health research. *All of Us* currently has more than 625,000 participants and access to electronic health records (EHRs) from 361,000 of those participants.

Approximately 436,000 participants have completed the initial steps of the program, and the program has collected more than 451,000 participant biosamples. *All of Us* data includes EHR data dating back 40 years and Fitbit data dating back more than 10 years. *All of Us* conforms to Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) data model. Newly released data in April 2023 include survey responses, physical measures, EHR data, genomic arrays, WGS, and Fitbit data. Greater than 80 percent of *All of Us* participants self-identify as underrepresented groups, including by race and ethnicity, sexual orientation, ability status, educational attainment, income, and geography.

In 2020, *All of Us* launched the Researcher Workbench, which is a cloud-based platform through which registered researchers can access *All of Us* curated and collected data, conduct analyses, and collaborate with other researchers. More than 5,000 researchers from more than 500 registered institutions currently use *All of Us*-collected participant data for various studies. *All of Us* is working to engage researchers from numerous National Institute of Health (NIH) Institutes, as well as minority-serving academic institutions. Researchers are authenticated by *All of Us* within hours of registration, which does not require Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval.

The [first paper published using *All of Us* data](#), led by Dr. Sally Baxter, predicted the risk of glaucoma surgery in participants diagnosed with primary open-angle glaucoma utilizing a machine learning approach. This study highlighted opportunities for ophthalmology researchers using the *All of Us* dataset. Other eye health and vision research opportunities include the following:

- Learning predictors of eye and systemic diseases from OCT
- Linking retinal images with genetics for Mendelian diseases
- Using proposed EyeWAS association between eye features and phenotype
- Analyzing nutrition effects on ocular diseases
- Assessing health disparities in ocular diseases
- Promoting drug target discovery
- Producing geospatial social determinants of health (SDOH) studies

Highlights of Systemic Disease Research from Large Cohort Studies

Novel Insights from Studying Aging Eyes

Cecilia Lee, MD, MS, University of Washington

The availability of big data and AI has created a new paradigm in medical research, in which big data can be leveraged to create novel connections between collected participant data and disease to produce insights of importance to meeting participants, particularly linkages between neurology and ophthalmology. More than 46 million people live with Alzheimer's disease and Alzheimer's disease related dementias (AD/ADRD), and this number is anticipated to triple by 2050. Researchers can leverage big data, including eye and retinal data, to identify risk factors for neuropathy in aging populations.

Researchers at the University of Washington and Kaiser Permanente Washington have been conducting a longitudinal study of individuals over age 65 or older called Adult Changes in Thought (ACT study since 1994. All enrollees are cognitively normal at the beginning of the recruitment, assessed via cognitive tests every 2 years, and followed until the development of AD/ADRD. Researchers analyzed longitudinal ophthalmic data and imaging collected as part of this study to determine whether participants with age-related macular degeneration (AMD), glaucoma, or diabetic retinopathy were at risk for developing AD/ADRD. For all three of the conditions, researchers found that individuals with AMD, diabetic retinopathy and early stage of glaucoma were at significantly higher risks of developing AD/ADRD than individuals without these eye diseases. A follow-up study also showed that the presence of diabetic retinopathy was more strongly associated with risks of AD/ADRD than detailed markers of diabetic nephropathy or indicators of kidney function highlighting the importance of eye related biomarkers in understanding dementia risks.

Research on novel connections between eye disease and risk factors for neurodegenerative conditions has helped clinicians identify interventions that may help lower these risks. For example, one [study](#) demonstrated a 30 percent decreased in risk for AD/ADRD in individuals who received cataract surgery compared to those who did not. This study received significant media attention and demonstrates the potential for researchers to generate novel connections between eye pathologies and systemic diseases that could lead to new areas of research and/or therapeutic approach. Cardiovascular risks are known to be identifiable through fundus photo and ocular imaging. The Artificial Intelligence Ready and Equitable Atlas for Diabetes Insights (AI-READI) project, part of the NIH Bridge2AI program, is also collecting data from multimodal ophthalmic imaging data with extensive systemic data including fitness tracking, continuous glucose monitoring, and genetics. Its purpose is to produce a flagship dataset from 4,000 participants that is ready for AI/machine learning algorithm development for insights on type 2 diabetes.

Optical Coherence Tomography and Large Cohort Studies: Advanced Ocular Imaging Program

Joseph Carroll, PhD, Medical College of Wisconsin

OCT is useful in detecting diseases, guiding therapies, evaluating outcomes, and finding novel associations between anatomy and genomics. The treatment of achromatopsia (ACHM) provides one example of using OCT to guide therapies. Advances in gene therapy have made it possible to restore cone function in individuals with ACHM, and a 2017 [study](#) showed that OCT can be used to characterize the natural progression of ACHM to identify the therapeutic window for this intervention.

OCT can also be used to evaluate the outcomes of therapeutic interventions. In macular telangiectasia (MacTel) patients, one [study](#) showed that OCT played a major role in determining the success of treatments for MacTel. Despite researcher interest in using OCT to identify AD/ADRD patients, Dr. Carroll noted that OCT alone is probably not sufficient, and that debate remains in the field over additional measures needed to identify AD/ADRD progression. Researchers using OCT images in the UKB dataset were able to produce novel connections in how genetics affect retinal anatomy. Other researchers published a [study](#) using OCT in a genome-wide association study (GWAS) to identify gene variants associated with different morphological retinal phenotypes.

Ophthalmic Research Using *All of Us*

Sally L. Baxter, MD, MSc, University of California, San Diego

Dr. Baxter presented her team's research using the *All of Us* database, noting that one study aim was to share insights from use of the *All of Us* Research Workbench with ophthalmologists and vision scientists. Glaucoma is the world's leading cause of irreversible blindness, and the team's researchers are studying the relationship between systemic attributes and the risks for glaucoma progression. They built a single-center predictive model—using data at University of California, San Diego—to identify predictors of the need for glaucoma surgical/procedural intervention, including vital signs, physical measurements, comorbid conditions, and medications. They validated this model using *All of Us* data and then developed new models using *All of Us* data. Importantly, predictive modeling using *All of Us* datasets with a large number of diverse participants achieved a superior predictive performance, compared to single-center models.

The *All of Us* dataset presents researchers with numerous opportunities to explore health disparities and SDOH, particularly if *All of Us* datasets include ocular imaging in the future. An *All of Us* ocular imaging collection demonstrates the potential to help researchers identify early biomarkers of systemic disease and aging. *All of Us* can represent a source of images for underrepresented populations who lack regular access to eye care. Challenges also remain in developing algorithms that correct for bias, which highlights the advantage of training AI on diverse datasets. The *All of Us* Researcher Workbench can help reduce barriers to research with

ease of access and use. By expanding the imaging data available in its dataset, *All of Us* could attract additional researchers, as well.

Panel Discussion: Opportunities for Advancing Research with Retinal Images and *All of Us*

Moderator: Kerry Goetz, National Eye Institute

Panelists: Cecilia Lee, University of Washington

Emily Chew, National Eye Institute

Michael Boland, Mass Eye and Ear, Harvard Medical School

Sally Baxter, University of California, San Diego

Systemic Disease Research Opportunities

Several high-impact systemic disease research areas could be advanced through the addition of ocular imaging to the *All of Us* dataset:

- Ocular imaging could provide insights into neurodegenerative diseases, such as AD/ADRD, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis. Amyloid angiopathy can be detected on OCT scans, which may have increased significance for AD/ADRD research for identifying attractive drug targets. OCT scans may also represent a less invasive and more time-efficient method of monitoring AD/ADRD disease progression than traditional MRI.
- Vascular disease and related systemic diseases, such as diabetes, are a fruitful area for ocular imaging studies. Research in systemic vascular disease, such as diabetes and hypertension, has benefited from optical coherence tomography (OCT) and OCT angiography (OCTA) and has potential to advance the field when combined with *All of Us* longitudinal data.
- Cardiovascular and metabolic diseases could be diagnosed and monitored with ocular images.
- Trauma detected using ocular imaging may have applications for military medical research.
- Auto-immune and inflammatory disorders could advance with the use of ocular imaging connected to *All of Us* datasets.

In addition, ocular imaging combined with other *All of Us* data such as social determinants of health and lifestyle surveys can help researchers to better understand interactions between lifestyle, systemic and behavioral factors, and eye health. Activities of daily living are impacted by vision loss—such as a reduced ability to read medication instructions, to interact with patient portals, and to drive a motor vehicle, and in turn vision loss can exacerbate preexisting barriers to accessing health care.

By combining longitudinal data with ocular imaging in diverse cohorts, researchers can better study diseases such as sickle cell retinopathy that affect underrepresented groups. The relatively inexpensive and noninvasive use of ocular imaging can also help researchers search

for biomarkers and early detection of risk factors for disease in vulnerable populations. Ocular imaging coupled with *All of Us* genomic and SDOH data can inform development of new risk models for disease. The predictive value of these risk models increases with the availability of diverse cohorts, such as the *All of Us* cohort, which can reveal differences in treatment outcomes across various populations.

Benefits to Participants

Dr. Sheri Schully, *All of Us* Deputy Chief Medical and Scientific Officer, stated that *All of Us* sees participants as key members of the program planning when adding new insights into their health. Part of that relationship involves providing a clear explanation of their contribution to science as a way of thanking them for their involvement with the program. Ocular imaging could be part of the information shared with *All of Us* participants. Clinically significant findings from an ocular image could be communicated to *All of Us* participants; however, clinical and legal implications fall outside the scope of this meeting. Clinically actionable findings could be communicated to individuals whose scans reveal these issues.

All of Us has an ethics module for proposed research projects, which the study team regularly reviews for potential updates. Overall, reliability and actionability of findings in the eye—as well as contributing systemic data—determine whether patient communication about risk factors is warranted. As one example, the UKB does not notify participants about evidence of potential disease, regardless of what ocular imaging reveals. For certain risk factors evident during an in-person visit (such as very high blood pressure), *All of Us* has established policies to recommend sending participants to local emergency departments. Meeting participants agreed on the need for consensus protocols regarding patient referrals stemming from clinically actionable findings in eye exams, because current guidance is not clear; however, participants also recognized that an ocular image is not a replacement for a full ophthalmic exam.

Challenges to Diverse Representation in Ophthalmological Research

Ocular imaging as part of *All of Us* can enable research in populations that are typically difficult to reach because of their lack of access to eye care. Large-scale ocular imaging allows for prediction of long-term outcomes and assessment of pre-disease states in these populations, whose data are not always included in datasets derived from routine eye care. However, health care survey data, including data collected by *All of Us*, are skewed toward populations with higher incomes and access to health care (and health insurance). Pilot studies specifically designed to conduct outreach in populations with more limited access to health care may be needed to equitably collect data.

Technology can both remove and create barriers to study inclusion. If expensive imaging equipment is available only in locations with high-income populations, then other populations with low incomes are missed. Meeting participants representing *All of Us* acknowledged this issue and are actively considering the most versatile imaging instruments that are also widely available.

Meeting participants acknowledged the potential for bias in conducting research with large datasets. EHR data can be biased because they are input by a clinician, while an ocular image produced by a machine may have more objective value and could potentially reduce bias. Workshop participants are also cognizant that new stigmas and biases could unintentionally arise.

Alternative Data Types for Potential Inclusion in *All of Us* Ocular Scans

Meeting participants presumed that OCT, OCTA, and color fundus photography would be used if ocular imaging were included in *All of Us* and were invited to consider other data types that could be useful. The current *All of Us* workflow, methodology, and sample size are important considerations for prioritizing data types collected. Imaging elements that could be collected also depend on the expertise of staff conducting ocular images and the availability of various technologies in a particular locale. In general, typical tests conducted during eye exams, such as visual acuity, eye pressure, and refraction, were compelling additions for meeting participants. Anterior segment imaging, external photography, eye movement, and axial lengths could also be useful data for *All of Us* to collect.

Staffing expertise can affect the inclusion of alternative imaging data types. *All of Us* would likely utilize research assistants for imaging, not ophthalmologists. Image quality can be affected if staff does not receive sufficient training to recognize when images need to be retaken; thus, alternative data types should utilize technology that is not difficult to operate. The TopCon Maestro 2, which produces simultaneous fundus photography and OCT scans, is relatively easy to operate and does not require eye dilation. UKB utilized non-experts for its eye scans; however, OCTA imaging may be difficult to conduct without specialized personnel. Common eye diseases can make obtaining high-quality images challenging, but automated acquisition and automated image grading can improve quality.

The availability and complexity of instrumentation may also affect the inclusion of alternative imaging modalities. Researchers should be flexible in their expectations of available imaging devices because the technology is constantly evolving. Portability and ease of use are important considerations for ocular imaging technology, which should be easy to operate by non-specialist technicians and compact enough to use in a variety of settings. Moreover, older, more frail populations may be unable to visit imaging clinics and require imaging technology that can be brought to them.

Meeting participants also considered what data types could be linked to ocular images that *All of Us* might collect. EHR modules that include ophthalmology data would be useful. An OMOP working group is assessing how to improve the standardization of ophthalmic data within EHRs, and data collection with *All of Us* could provide a helpful use case. Also of interest to participants was medical claims data that includes relevant information such as cataract surgery. Meeting participants found that genetic data, which include endophenotypes for ocular disease, offer compelling research opportunities when paired with ocular imaging data.

Dr. Geoff Ginsburg noted that *All of Us* is specifically considering various types of data linkages, including geospatial data that can be linked to CDC's Environmental Justice Index.

Panel Discussion: Building Tools and Resources for Innovative Analysis

Moderator: Afrouz Anderson, National Institute for Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering

Panelists: Aaron Lee, University of Washington

Daniel Hammer, Food and Drug Administration

Joseph Carroll, Medical College of Wisconsin

Zhongdi Chu, Verana Health

Potential Types of Imaging Data for Use and Their Potential Challenges in the *All of Us* Researcher Workbench

OCT imaging has great research value, and several devices are available on the market. Home systems are also available, but data about access to these devices may be biased. Spectral domain OCT shows great potential for facilitating new discoveries and is scalable and cost-effective. Panelists also considered color fundus photography to be essential. Another recommendation is the use of OCTA imaging. Some devices can combine these modalities, which may help reduce costs and data and image quality variability. Volumetric data, retinal thickness, and segmentation layer thickness data could also be useful to collect.

Data storage and associated costs complicate imaging data collection. Full OCT volumes may be too large for most researchers to use. Foveal B-scan and fundus photography may be an economical choice. En-face images require less storage than other data types and should be made available for researchers, at minimum. OCT is often used by researchers to measure layer thicknesses, rather than analyzing the imaging data itself, which provides a compelling reason to segment the OCT data and provide measurements instead of full image volumes. Automation could be used to help segment these data.

Instrumentation matters in terms of image quality, and the availability of scanning equipment will vary depending on the locale. Because study participants typically do not want their pupils dilated, scanning laser ophthalmoscopy (SLO) can be used to collect fundus images. SLO produces less ungradable images than other devices; however, SLO-capable devices may not be widely available. Participants agreed that more devices (rather than less) distributed across study centers is the most effective means for producing an adequate volume of data for researchers. Participants also agreed that utilizing devices from multiple manufacturers allows for more robust AI training; Bridge2AI plans to use this strategy in its program.

Metadata and Physical Measurements for Enabling Research Applications

Several factors affect the types of metadata that could enable research applications, including interoperability, standardization, and ease of use. *All of Us* could serve as a use case for applying Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) interoperability standards, which may encourage vendors to adopt these standards. The production of metadata could be accomplished by coupling EHR eye exam data with ocular images.

Tiered access for image data is preferable for managing the storage needs and computational resources of large ocular image repositories. Tiered data access like those currently available in the *All of Us* Researcher Workbench will allow for privacy preservation of the participant images and data. Panelists proposed that lower access tiers could contain summary metrics of image libraries and higher tiers could contain full volumetric OCT data. Data curation would be needed to manage tiered computational needs—automation of this curation, assisted by deep learning approaches, could allow for scalability of the collection.

Panelists debated how to create training sets for deep learning algorithms. Manual grading of images may recapitulate biases, whereas algorithmic grading coupled with clinical metadata may provide new insights. Alternatively, grading could be crowdsourced by making some workbench data sharable. Creation of metadata by clinicians, rather than deep learning alone, was deemed necessary by several panelists. In addition to training datasets, panelists were divided on the appropriate approach to creating metadata to curate ocular image collections. Computational phenotyping for glaucoma was considered worth pursuing, because of the frequency of misdiagnoses. Some panelists expressed reservations about automated phenotyping without human input. However, most panelists recognized that bias remains an issue for any potential metadata that is based on what clinicians might enter in EHRs. Panelists did not resolve the debate on whether curation of metadata should be manual or automated, but they acknowledged that the design of *All of Us* image collections would be informed by how this debate is resolved.

Annotation Requirements for AI

Data segmentation of structural OCT (within DICOM standards) would be useful for setting up image collections where AI and machine learning can be employed in research endeavors. However, segmentation lines are not always accurate and machine learning models will need to be developed to improve accuracy. Regardless of how the data are segmented, data formats should be open source, rather than proprietary, to maximize access to image resources for scientific discovery.

Data provenance and traceability of images is a key priority. DICOM and OMOP frameworks could be applied to ensure that the provenance of images is preserved, and the source of annotations is evident. OMOP instrument and imaging working groups are addressing this issue.

Inclusion of Physiological Measures

Visual acuity is a particularly useful physiological measure to capture. Several panelists recommended axial length as another measure to capture, recognizing that this increases expense. Information about prior cataract surgery and other eye surgeries would be helpful, as well. *All of Us* is planning follow-up visits with study participants to add more physiological measures, which could include additional ocular imaging.

Both OMOP and DICOM use physiological measurement data, and the architects of image collection repositories should take care not to add redundant data, which makes image

curation more difficult. *All of Us* collection designers should be aware of the image quality issue when considering the inclusion of physiological measures; eye images captured in community settings must account for staff skill level, varying types of available imaging equipment, and appropriately darkened settings for imaging. Thus, EHR data became an important source of physiological measures to accompany the images.

Potential Tools and Platforms for Advancing Research Using Ocular Imaging Data

DICOM standardization is an important starting point for a myriad of image analyses. Jupyter Notebooks may be a useful platform for image analysis because of their open source, interoperative capabilities. The Google computing platform can also support researchers utilizing various deep learning systems. Several panelists highlighted the potential of tools that account for pixel intensity. Panelists also supported the idea of workspaces for sharing tools and cohort notebooks within the scientific community; however, workspace designers should be mindful of space requirements for deep learning models, which can be substantial.

Analytical Methods and Tools for Optimizing and Standardizing Potential OCT Imaging Data within The *All of Us* Dataset

Beyond DICOM standards for OCT and open-source libraries facilitated by Jupyter Notebooks, panelists expressed concern about support for scientists and developers. *All of Us* produces FAQs, allows users to submit tickets, and holds office hours and user forums to field technical questions. Superusers could help disseminate the capabilities and best practices of using *All of Us* datasets. *All of Us* also recently released a [funding announcement](#) for the development of tools to foster community sourcing of methods and analyses.

Closing Remarks

Geoff Ginsburg, MD, PhD, All of Us Research Program

Dr. Ginsburg thanked panelists for their insights. He observed that the workshop operates at the intersection of clinical therapeutics, ocular data, engineering, and population health science. Because of the efforts of workshop participants, ocular imaging will become the vanguard of the *All of Us* dataset.

Several important themes emerged from the workshop, including the value of ocular imaging in predicting systemic diseases, such as diabetes and vascular diseases, and in informing risk prediction models for other diseases. Dr. Ginsburg commented that coupling genetic data with imaging can help build polygenic risk scores, including for eye-related disease. Novel analytic methods using imaging data in *All of Us* datasets and data standardization also emerged as important themes.

Dr. Ginsburg stated that the NEI-NIBIB-*All of Us* collaboration is a catalyst for health equity research in underserved and underrepresented populations. Ocular imaging can enable research into the mechanistic aspects of disease and enhance the ability of clinicians to detect diseases earlier. *All of Us* aims to build a portfolio of ocular imaging and AI tools to accelerate

research. He implored panelists to continually consider how to translate research findings to the clinical community.

Appendix A: Meeting Agenda

12:30 pm

Welcome and Program Introduction

Kerry E. Goetz, MS
Associate Director, Office of Data Science and Health Informatics
National Eye Institute
National Institutes of Health

Michael F. Chiang, MD
Director, National Eye Institute
National Institutes of Health

Bruce Tromberg, PhD
Director, National Institute for Biomedical Imaging and
Bioengineering

12:45 pm

Current Landscape of Reginal Imaging Research and Databases

UK Biobank: Scope of Eye and Vision Data

Paul J. Foster, PhD FRCS(ed) FRCOphth FRCS(Eng)
Professor, Ophthalmic Epidemiology
University College of London

Scientific Opportunities with the *All of Us* Research Program

Josh Denny, MD MS
CEO, All of Us Research Program

1:00 pm

Highlights of Ophthalmologic Research Done with Large Cohort Studies

Novel Insights from Studying Aging Eyes

Cecilia Lee, MD, MS
Associate Professor of Ophthalmology
University of Washington

OCT and Large Cohort Studies: Advanced Ocular Imaging Program

Joseph Carroll, PhD
Professor in Ophthalmology
Medical College of Wisconsin

Ophthalmic Research Using *All of Us*

Sally L. Baxter, MD MSc

Assistant Professor of Ophthalmology and Biomedical Informatics
University of California, San Diego

1:40 pm

Break

1:50 pm

Panel Discussion: Opportunities for Advancing Research with Retinal Images and *All of Us*

Moderator: Kerry Goetz, National Eye Institute

Panelists:

Cecilia Lee, University of Washington

Emily Chew, National Eye Institute

Michael Boland, Massachusetts Eye and Ear & Harvard Medical School

Sally Baxter, University of California San Diego

3:20 pm

Panel Discussion: Building Tools and Resources for Innovative Analysis

Moderator: Afrouz Anderson, NIBIB

Panelists:

Aaron Lee, University of Washington

Daniel Hammer, Food and Drug Administration

Joseph Carroll, Medical College of Wisconsin

Zhongdi Chu, Verana Health

4:50 pm

Closing Remarks

Geoff Ginsburg, MD, PhD

Chief Medical and Scientific Research Officer

All of Us Research Program

Appendix B: Workshop Participant List

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